

Determination of chromium, copper, manganese, nickel and zinc by flame atomic absorption spectrometry after separation of bentonite modified with trioctylamine

Yıldız Kalebaşı Aktaş* and Hilmi İbar

Department of Chemistry, Trakya University, 22030 Edirne, Turkey

E-mail : yilaktas@yahoo.com Fax : 90-284-2137053

Manuscript received 6 May 2003, revised 22 September 2004, accepted 8 October 2004

Bentonite modified with trioctylamine is developed for the separation and pre-concentration of chromium, copper, manganese, nickel and zinc prior to their determination by Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (FAAS). The retention and recovery of the analyte elements have been investigated by applying column techniques where in Cr^{III} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} are quantitatively retained by the collector at pH 6 or above. For a column with 0.3 g of bentonite modified with trioctylamine and a flow rate of 5.0 mL min^{-1} , it can quantitatively adsorb the trace heavy metals and quantitative desorption of the elements can be realized by elution with 10 mL of 1 mol L^{-1} HNO_3 . Low blank values of the collector have served as important advantage and recoveries are found to be $99.9 \pm 2\%$, $98.8 \pm 3\%$, $99.6 \pm 2\%$, $97.2 \pm 3\%$ and $87.3 \pm 4\%$ for Cr, Cu, Zn, Mn and Ni, respectively, at 95% confidence level. In the presence of Na^+ , K^+ and Mg^+ the analyte elements are quantitatively separated and recovered. The relative standard deviations for the determinations are found to be 0.1–1.9%. Detection limits (3σ) are 1.7 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Cr, 2.2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Cu, 2.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Zn, 2.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Mn and 2.8 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Ni. The method has been applied to analysis of the Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni and Zn studied in waste waters.

The direct determination of trace metals found in waste waters is difficult and in many instances it is necessary to employ pre-concentration procedures to enhance the concentration of the analyte in the solution to be determined. Therefore column technique is a very useful tool for such difficult analysis performance. It allows simultaneous trace elements separation from pre-concentration prior to be subsequent determination by flame AAS. Many methods have been proposed for the trace metal removal. Sorption¹⁻³, flow-pre-concentration systems⁴, liquid-liquid extraction⁵, co-precipitation^{6,7}, ion exchange^{8,9} and adsorption^{10,11} have been successfully applied as separation procedures.

Especially, ion exchangers have been suggested to be effective and reliable collectors for pre-concentrations in off/on line combination with atomic spectrometric methods. Because of the variations in the compositions of the soil and clay minerals from different localities, each requires specific study.

In this study, bentonite is modified with trioctylamine (T-B) and its use for the pre-concentration and separation of chromium, copper, manganese, nickel and zinc prior to their determination by flame AAS is described. It is an inexpensive clay mineral readily available in Turkey.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A Unicam Model 929 atomic absorption spectrometer with air/acetylene was used for flame measurements. The instrumental conditions for each element were taken from the instrumental manual.

pH values were determined with an Orion 720A Model pH meter using a combined electrode.

Reagents :

All reagents used were of the highest purity available and at least of analytical-reagent grade. Mixed standard solutions of the elements Cr, Cu, Zn, Mn and Ni were prepared by appropriate dilution of 1000 mg mL^{-1} stock AAS solutions (Alfa Aesar). Reference solutions were prepared daily by further dilution with distilled water. The pH values of metal solutions were subsequently adjusted to the desired values using hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide solutions (0.1 N).

An activated bentonite from the west part of Turkey was used (from Enez). Chemical composition of the sample is (percentage) : SiO_2 , 54.65; Al_2O_3 , 19.10; Fe_2O_3 , 7.32; MgO , 1.61; CaO , 0.88; Na_2O , 0.73; K_2O , 0.02.

Aktaş *et al.* : Determination of chromium, copper, manganese, nickel and zinc by flame atomic absorption *etc.*

Preparation of trioctylamine-modified bentonite :

At first, bentonite was pre-purified with hydrochloric acid (4 mol L⁻¹) and washed with distilled water. The highly pure bentonite was dried at 150°C for one day. Sorbent was prepared by loading trioctylamine on bentonite. 4 mL trioctylamine was added on 2 g bentonite and stirred and mixture obtained was stirred for 3 h. After that mixture was dried and heated at 80–100°C for 3 h.

Column procedure :

A small portion of glass wool washed with HCl and distilled water was placed at the bottom of a glass column (1.3 × 20 cm) and 0.3 g. T-B was placed into the column. Then another small glass wool plug was inserted on the top of the T-B. The height of filling became about 0.7 cm. A definite volume of a solution adjusted to pH 6 was passed through the column at a flow rate of about 5.0 mL min⁻¹ which was found to be optimum. The elements collected on the T-B were eluted with 10 mL of 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and determined by FAAS. The optimum flow rate for elution of the analyte elements was 5.0 mL min⁻¹. All the results given in this paper are the averages of at least four repetitive determinations.

Evaluation of retention :

The effect of the pH on retention of the metal ions was studied; 10 mL mixed aqueous standard solution of Cr, Cu, Zn, Mn and Ni with concentrations in the range 5–10 µg mL⁻¹ depending on the sensitivity of flame AAS measurement for each element was buffered to a suitable pH value and passed through the columns packed with investigated sorbent. Retained metals were then eluted with 10 mL, 1 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid. The amount of metals was determined by flame AAS. Recoveries (R%) calculated against the theoretical concentrations.

Results and discussion

The loading capacity of the bentonite modified with trioctylamine (T-B) is 2.67 mg Cr/g, 2.11 mg Cu/g, 3.22 mg Mn/g, 4.64 mg Ni/g and 6.67 mg Zn/g T-B. The effect of the pH on the retention of Cr^{III}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} using the column method is investigated. The elements studied are quantitatively (100%) retained on the T-B in the pH range of 6 to 9 and eluted quantitatively after treating the loaded T-B with 1 mol/L HNO₃. The recoveries of the trace metals are given in Table 1. The elements studied were quantitatively recovered at the end of complete procedure. As can be seen from the table, relative standard deviations were between 0.1 and 1.9%. The relative standard deviations of the recovering values, an accuracy and preci-

sion of the above findings suggest that the proposed method could be used for the determination of trace metals in environmental water samples. The detection limits (3σ, n = 10) for chromium, copper, zinc, manganese and nickel from the blank solution were found to be 1.7 µg L⁻¹, 2.2 µg L⁻¹, 2.1 µg L⁻¹, 2.4 µg L⁻¹ and 2.8 µg L⁻¹, respectively.

Table 1. Recoveries of the elements studied; T-B, 0.3 g (pH 6); sample volume 50 mL; 1 M HNO₃ (10 mL) as an eluent

Element (µg)	Added	Found ^a
Cr	100.0	99.9 ± 0.1
Cu	100.0	98.4 ± 0.5
Zn	100.0	98.6 ± 0.3
Mn	100.0	97.5 ± 0.8
Ni	100.0	96.6 ± 1.9

^aAverage of five determinations with 95% confidence level.

The contact time between sample solution and T-B for the completion of the quantitative retention as well as between eluent and loaded T-B for the quantitative elution were investigated as another important parameter. By using the column described in the experimental section, the metals are adsorbed quantitatively at a flow-rate of 5.0 mL/min at pH 6 and eluted with 1 mol/L nitric acid at an elution rate of 5.0 mL/min.

Table 2. Determination of Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni and Zn in waste waters (T-B, 0.3 g; pH 6; sample 100 mL; eluent volume 10 mL; eluent 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ for Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni and Zn)

Element	Waste water ^a (µg mL ⁻¹)	Added (µg mL ⁻¹)	Found ^a (µg mL ⁻¹)
Cr	0.693 ± 0.3	2.00	2.69 ± 0.2
Cu	0.085 ± 0.1	2.00	2.08 ± 0.1
Mn	0.366 ± 0.2	2.00	2.30 ± 0.3
Ni	0.553 ± 0.2	2.00	2.50 ± 0.4
Zn	0.150 ± 0.3	2.00	2.11 ± 0.4

^aAverage of four determinations with 95% confidence level.

After a series of experiments, the optimum column conditions were determined. In the presence of Na⁺, K⁺ and Mg⁺ (50 mg/L), the analyte elements are quantitatively retained at a flow-rate of 5.0 mL/min at pH 6 and eluted with 1 mol/L nitric acid at an elution rate of 5.0 mL/min. The method was applied for the determination chromium, copper, manganese, nickel and zinc in waste water samples. An aliquot (100 mL) of the water sample (alkaline) was adjusted to pH 6 with 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HCl, filtered to remove suspended material and then subjected to the general procedure. The analytical results are shown in Table 2. The results are in good agreement regarding the original concentration found in the samples and the added analyte concentrations. Except real samples (waste waters), all the solutions passed through the column were kept to 10 mL. Because of their low metal contents, waste water volumes

passed through the column were increased up to 100 mL. Up to 100 mL solution volumes passed through the column have no effect on quantitative adsorption of metals. This shows that the new adsorbent T-B is useful for the pre-concentration of trace elements in many water samples. In addition, the proposed column procedure for the trace elements pre-concentration is simple, repeatable and less susceptible to contamination, which is very useful for routine analysis of waters.

Conclusion :

Sorbent on the base of bentonite modified with trioctylamine is proposed as an effective column packing material for pre-concentration and separation of trace analytes. The T-B column is easily regenerated by washing with a large volume of water after the elution and can be used repeatedly. The compositions of bentonite may vary widely in clays and soils. The presence of a bentonite component in clays and soils may significantly affect the properties of such materials, and hence is of importance in agriculture, construction engineering, ceramics, etc. It has been extensively used in drilling processes, but few scientists have used clay mineral in water and waste water pollution control. The new collector shows that sufficient adsorption capacity for chromium, copper, manganese, nickel and zinc above pH 6. T-B provides a high flow rate for the column process to obtain quantitative retention. Using the

column procedure, the elements studied can be reliably determined in the presence of Na⁺, K⁺ and Mg⁺. A column procedure with flame AAS determination of trace analytes is developed for the analysis of Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni and Zn in waste waters.

References

1. Y. K. Aktas and H. İbar, *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin*, 2004, **13**, 156.
2. A. S. Sheta, A. M. Falatah, M. S. Al-Sewaillem, E. M. Khaled and A. S. H. Sallam, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 2003, **61**, 127.
3. J. Lee, J. Choi and J. Park, *Chemosphere*, 2002, **49**, 1309.
4. V. Carbonelli, A. Salvador and M. de la Guardia, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1992, **342**, 529.
5. Y. K. Aktas and H. İbar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 1.
6. Ü. Divrikli and L. Elci, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 2002, **452**, 231.
7. B. Welz, S. Xo and M. Sperling, *Applied Spectroscopy*, 1991, **45**, 1433.
8. S. Caroli, A. Alimonti, F. Petrucci and Z. Horvath, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1991, **248**, 241.
9. S. Kaufhold, R. Dohrmann, K. Ufer and F. M. Meyer, *Applied Clay Science*, 2002, **22**, 145.
10. O. Abollino, M. Aceto, M. Malandrino, C. Sarzanini and E. Mentasti, *Water Research*, 2003, **37**, 1619.
11. R. Nascem and S. S. Tahir, *Water Research*, 2001, **35**, 3982.